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Azatriiterpenes. Part-VII. Synthesis of 2-Eno-[2,3-g]tetrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidines of Pentacyclic Triterpenes†

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HETEROSTEROIDS in recent years have gained great importance because of their modified physiological activity and sometimes with completely changed biological activity¹⁻⁴. To develop new azasteroids of biological interest, Bajwa and Sykes⁵ synthesised various steroidal 2-eno[2,3-g]-tetrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidines by the reaction of steroidal 3-keto-2-hydroxymethylene derivatives with 5-aminotetrazole. As an application of this approach⁵ we report herein some 2-eno[2,3-g]-tetrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidines of pentacyclic triterpenes.

2-Hydroxymethylene derivatives⁶ of methyl oleonate (1), lupenone (2) and methyl betulonate (3) were condensed with 5-aminotetrazole in absolute ethanol to obtain the desired compounds 4-6. The assignment of structures was based on the observation of Bajwa and Sykes⁵ for 2-eno[2,3-g]-tetrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidines. Thus in the nmr spectra of 4-6, a sharp signal around δ 8.67 (5'-H) conforms to the angular isomers as according to Bajwa and Sykes⁵ the other isomeric structure ([3,2-f]tetrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidine) is expected to give a broadened singlet for 7'-H due to a small longrange coupling with methylene protons. Also, in agreement to Bajwa and Sykes⁵, in the present case tetrazolopyrimidines (4-6) exist in equilibrium with their azido forms in solution which is demon-

strated in the ir spectra of the compounds in chloroform ($\nu_{\max}$ 2140 cm^{-1} for azido function). The nmr spectra of all the three 2-eno[2,3-g]tetrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidines (4-6) showed a sharp signal around δ 8.1 (1H, 6'-H of azido form) and another around δ 8.6 (1H, 5'-H of tetrazolo form). The spectral data clearly indicate that the tetrazolo form and the azido form exist in equilibrium in solution. This is also supported by presence of two spots on the tlc of the condensation products.

Experimental

M.ps. were recorded using Bio-chem melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. The nmr spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded on a EM-360 (60 MHz) nmr spectrometer with TMS as the internal standard. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord 237 spectrophotometer.

3-Keto-2-hydroxymethylene derivatives of pentacyclic triterpenes were prepared by the usual method⁶.

A typical experiment for the condensation of 5-aminotetrazole with 3-keto-2-hydroxymethylene derivatives of pentacyclic triterpenes (1-3). Isolation of 2-eno[2,3-g]tetrazolo[1,5-a]pyrimidines of pentacyclic triterpenes (4-6): A solution of the compound 1-3 (700 mg) 5-aminotetrazole (250 mg) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 12 h and then evaporated to dryness in vacuum. The residue was adsorbed over neutral alumina (Acme) and eluted with petroleum ether (500 cm^3) and benzene (1.5 dm^3). Petroleum ether eluate did not yield any residue. Benzene eluate yielded 2-eno[2,3-g]-

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tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine (~ 500 mg) which was finally purified by crystallisation from CHCl_3 –methanol as colourless needles *methyl 2-eno[2,3-*g*]tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine-olean-12-en-28-oate* (4), m.p 135–40° (Found C, 72.6; H, 8.45; N, 12.7. $\text{C}_{88}\text{H}_{47}\text{O}_2\text{N}_5$ requires: C, 72.66; H, 8.62; N, 12.84%); δ 8.67 (s, 5'-H), 8.21 (s, 6'-H), 5.3 (1H, t, 12-H), 3.65 (3H, s, COOMe) and 0.9–2.5 (21H, 7×Me); ν_{max} 2145 (N_s), 1720 (ester C=O), 1565, 1555, 1415 and 1380 cm^{-1} (characteristic of pyrimidine ring); *2-eno[2,3-*g*]tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine-lup-20(29)-ene* (5); m.p 165–70° (Found C, 76.5; H, 9.2; N, 13.8. $\text{C}_{82}\text{H}_{47}\text{N}_5$ requires C, 76.64; H, 9.36; N, 13.97%) δ 8.6 (s, 5'-H of tetrazolo form), 8.2 (s, 6'-H of azido form), 4.7 (2H, d, C=CH₂) and 0.9–2.5 (21H, 7×Me), ν_{max} 2140 (N_s), 1565, 1555, 1415 and 1380 cm^{-1} (characteristic of pyrimidine ring); *methyl-2-eno[2,3-*g*]tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine-lup-20(29)-en-28-oate* (6): m.p 135–40° (Found C, 72.6; H, 8.45; N, 12.7. $\text{C}_{88}\text{H}_{47}\text{O}_2\text{N}_5$ requires C, 72.66; H, 8.62; N, 12.84%); δ 8.67 (s, 5'-H of tetrazolo form), 8.2 (s, 6'-H of azido form), 4.7 (2H, d, C=CH₂), 3.65 (3H, s, COOMe) and 0.9–2.5 (18H, 6×Me); ν_{max} 2140 (N_s), 1720 cm^{-1} (methyl ester C=O), 1565, 1555, 1415 and 1380 cm^{-1} (characteristic of pyrimidine ring).

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Pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines. Synthesis and Reaction of 2-Amino-3-cyanopyrroles

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IMPORTANT antibiotics tubercidin¹, toyocamycin¹ and sangivamycin² have pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine moiety in their structures. 4-Amino/hydroxy-

pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines have been reported to possess analgesic, anti-inflammatory, CNS depressant, anticonvulsant and sedative activities^{3,4}. In the present paper, we report the synthesis of 4-amino-pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines and some new 2-amino-3-cyanopyrroles, important intermediates for various fused heterocycles.

(2-Bromo-1-arylalkylidene)propanedinitriles (1) when condensed with various aromatic amines under mild Gewald reaction condition⁵, 2-amino-3-cyanopyrroles (2) were obtained, which on heterocyclisation with formamide in DMF/HCOOH afforded 4-amino-5,7-disubstitutedpyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (3).

R = C_6H_5 , 4- $\text{OH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, 4- $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, 4- $\text{ClO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$,

R₁ = C_6H_5 , 4- $\text{OH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, 4- $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, 4- $\text{ClO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, 4- $\text{BrO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, 4- $\text{IO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$.

It was observed during the synthesis of 2-amino-1,4-disubstituted-3-cyanopyrroles (2) that the reaction was unsuccessful in the presence of a strong electron-releasing group such as NH_2 or OH and a strong electron-withdrawing NO_2 group in the 4-position of primary aromatic amines. Further, the reaction failed to yield the desired 2 when meta-substituted-aromatic amines were used.

Ir (KBr) spectra of 2-amino-3-cyanopyrroles (2) exhibited bands near 3400 and 3320 (NH_2), 2200 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) and 1600 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{C}$ ring), and 4-amino-5,7-disubstituted-7H-pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (3) showed bands near 3470, 3300 and 3100 cm^{-1} (NH_2), ~1640 (NH_2) and 1590–1480 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ ring). The absence of a strong band ~2200 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) was indicative of the completion of reaction between 2 and formamide.

Compounds 3g, h, j failed to show any anticancer activity when screened against Leukemia tumor at the doses of 60, 120 and 240 mg/kg.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin–Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. The purity of compounds were checked by tlc using silica gel-G and spots were visualised by exposing the dried plates to iodine vapours.